

Data Management Plan: SHAREWIND - Shared anchors for floating wind turbines

Version 1

Description

This document describes the lifecycle of the data to be collected, processed, and generated by the SHAREWIND project. It provides a summary of anticipated data types, formats, and structures, detailing the considerations and strategies to implement FAIR data principles. The current Data Management Plan includes a data summary, considerations for making data FAIR, details on other research outputs, allocation of resources, data security, ethics, and other relevant issues. The Data Management Plan for the SHAREWIND project is a dynamic document that will be updated throughout the development of the project. This version of the document represents the first submission of the Data Management Plan in December 2023.

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Shared anchors for
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Researchers

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Organizations

UNIV. GUSTAVE EIFFEL - Département Géotechnique, environnement, risques naturels et sciences de la terre

Datasets

Title: [Dataset: SHAREWIND - Shared anchors for floating wind turbines](#)

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

The SHAREWIND project aims to generate comprehensive datasets through a combination of experiments and numerical simulations. The dataset will encompass various formats to capture the diverse nature of the research:

CSV (.csv) files: These files will contain measured data from sensors utilized in centrifuge experiments and data points derived from processed numerical models.

MP4 files: Video recordings of the experiments will be stored in this format, providing visual documentation of the research processes.

JPEG files: Images and photographs relevant to the experiments and simulations will be represented in JPEG format.

Text files (.txt): Metadata associated with the dataset will be stored in plain text files, providing essential information about the experimental setup and numerical models.

DXF files: Computer-assisted drawings of schemas will be documented in DXF format, facilitating a visual representation of experimental and numerical configurations.

PDF and .tex files: Text documents, including research reports and technical documentation, will be stored in both PDF and LaTeX (.tex) formats.

Dataset Description

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

The SHAREWIND project primarily involves the generation of new data obtained from measurements of sensors installed in models subjected to testing within the geotechnical centrifuge of the Université Gustave Eiffel. Additionally, data will be generated through numerical simulations employing the finite element method. While the focus is on creating new data within the project, if there arises a need to repurpose external datasets, careful consideration will be given to factors such as copyright, permissions, and ethical aspects for reuse. In such cases, the License Clearance Tool will be utilized to ensure compliance with relevant licensing agreements.

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Experimental

The described dataset for the SHAREWIND project comprises both experimental and simulation data, with the primary focus on studying the load capacity of suction caissons installed in soft clay. The experiments and subsequent data analysis will be conducted by Cristian Soriano. The data collection, analysis, and visualization processes will be thoroughly documented in README files and data reports.

To enhance understanding, each data file will include descriptions based on the type of centrifuge experiments performed. The data files will be organized in columns, with each column assigned a description such as the identification of the sensor or the measured magnitude. Additionally, all files will incorporate version numbers for effective version control and traceability. This approach

ensures clarity and structure in the dataset, facilitating both internal and external use.

1.1.5 What is its format?

The SHAREWIND project will generate data from experiments and numerical simulations. Non-proprietary format files will be produced to guarantee the interoperability and accessibility of the data. The generated data will be in the following formats:

CSV (.csv) files: Containing measured data from sensors in centrifuge experiments and data points of processed numerical models.

MP4 files: For video recordings of the experiments.

JPEG files: For images and photos.

Text files (.txt): For metadata.

DXF files: For computer-assisted drawings of schemas.

PDF and .tex files: For text documents.

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

The data set volume is between 1 TB to 5 TB

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To share information

- To keep on record

In the context of the SHAREWIND project, data will be collected to establish the loading capacity of suction anchors installed in soft clay. Experimental data will be retrieved from sensors measuring forces, displacements, and excess pore pressures in the soil (Objective 1). This experimental data forms the foundation for calibrating numerical models of suction caissons under both monotonic and cyclic multidirectional loading (Objective 2). The overarching goal is to advance our understanding of the performance of suction caissons in soft clay, contributing valuable insights to geotechnical engineering practices and optimizing the design and implementation of such anchors in real-world applications.

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

The data for the SHAREWIND project will originate from measurements obtained through sensors installed in physical models to be tested in the geotechnical centrifuge of the Université Gustave Eiffel. The data collection will involve multiple sources, including displacement sensors, force sensors, pore pressure transducers, video cameras, digital cameras, and output worksheets from numerical simulations.

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Industry

The experimental data generated in the SHAREWIND project can be useful for the calibration of numerical models intended to validate the load capacity of suction anchors installed in normally consolidated clay. The data, expressed in simplified relationships of forces vs displacements and forces vs time, holds significant utility for both researchers and industry practitioners. Other researchers in the field of geotechnical engineering and anchor design can reuse this data to enhance their own studies and validate their models. Likewise, industry practitioners involved in the design and implementation of suction anchors can benefit from the insights provided by this dataset to optimize their practices. The openness and accessibility of the data contribute to its utility and potential impact across a spectrum of research and practical applications.

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

Yes

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

Yes

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

Yes

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

Data identifiers

DOI

All data will be made openly available throughout Zenodo repository <https://zenodo.org/> . Further details of the data repository are reported in re3data: <https://www.re3data.org/repository/r3d100010468>

In Zenodo, datasets will be assigned a globally unique persistent identifier in the form of a Digital Object Identifier (DOI). This DOI ensures that the datasets are citable, persistently available, and findable, enhancing their visibility and traceability in scholarly communications. The use of DOIs aligns with best practices for research data management, contributing to the long-term accessibility and impact of the SHAREWIND project's datasets.

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

DataCite Metadata Schema

All datasets deposited in Zenodo will be accompanied by rich metadata that complies with the DataCite Metadata Schema. This metadata includes essential information such as title, author/creator, abstract, keywords, and other key attributes necessary for effective discovery and identification. By adhering to established metadata standards, we ensure that the datasets are well-described and can be easily accessed, interpreted, and utilized by the research community. The inclusion of comprehensive metadata aligns with best practices in research data management, promoting the discoverability and reuse of the SHAREWIND project's datasets.

3.1.1.3 What type(s) of metadata?

Descriptive

In the project repository, a comprehensive set of metadata will be included to describe the datasets and enhance their discoverability. The metadata will include the following elements:

Data Persistent ID (DOI): A unique identifier assigned to each dataset for citation and persistent access.

Publication Date: The date when the dataset is published or made publicly available.

Title: A concise and descriptive title that represents the content of the dataset.

Author(s): The individuals or entities responsible for creating the dataset.

Contact: Information about the person or entity to contact for inquiries or collaboration related to the dataset.

Description: A detailed narrative describing the content, context, and purpose of the dataset.

Subject: The main subject or topic covered by the dataset.

Keywords: Relevant keywords or phrases that aid in the discovery of the dataset.

Related Publication(s): Citations or references to publications related to the dataset.

Language: The language(s) in which the dataset is presented.

Producer: Information about the entity or person responsible for producing the dataset.

Deposit Date: The date when the dataset is deposited or made available in the repository.

Type of Data: A categorization indicating the nature or type of data represented in the dataset.

By including these metadata elements, we aim to provide a comprehensive and well-documented description of the datasets, fostering their accessibility and reuse within the research community.

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

No

3.1.1.5 Please provide URL/Description of used vocabularies

Not applicable.

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

Yes

3.1.1.7 How are searchable metadata provided?

- Metadata repository
- Other

All data, including datasets, publications, and metadata, will be made openly available through the data repository. Keywords will be assigned to enhance discoverability by search engines. The metadata of each record is indexed and searchable directly in Zenodo's search engine immediately after publishing. Additionally, metadata of each record is sent to DataCite servers during DOI registration and indexed there. Zenodo datasets are also indexed in Google Dataset Search, further expanding the visibility and accessibility of the metadata across various search platforms. This comprehensive approach ensures that the metadata associated with SHAREWIND project records is readily discoverable by users and search engines alike.

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

Yes

As part of the provisions to follow FAIR principles, keywords will be provided in the datasets' metadata. This approach is integral to enhancing the findability of the datasets, making them more accessible and discoverable for researchers, practitioners, and other stakeholders. The inclusion of keywords aligns with best practices in research data management, ensuring that the SHAREWIND project's datasets are well-indexed and easily locatable, fostering their potential for future reuse and impact.

3.1.1.9 Are metadata harvestable?

Yes

All data, including datasets, publications, and metadata, will be made openly available throughout the data repository in Zenodo. Both data and metadata are harvestable using the OAI-PMH protocol, utilizing the record identifier and the collection name. This protocol facilitates standardized information exchange, allowing external services and repositories to efficiently harvest and integrate the metadata associated with the SHAREWIND project's records. The use of the OAI-PMH protocol aligns with interoperability

standards, enhancing the accessibility and integration of the project's metadata into broader data ecosystems.

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

ZENODO

<https://zenodo.org/>

The project repository for the SHAREWIND project will be on Zenodo. A community link has been created in Zenodo to organize all the outputs and publications associated with the project:

<https://zenodo.org/communities/sharewind>.

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

Yes

- Follows repository standards
- Details terms of use
- Has an open access content policy

- Supports back up
- Provides Open Access content (free at the point of use)
- Follows metadata standards
- Uses non-proprietary formats
- Supports mid- and long-term preservation

3.2.1.4 Add appropriate arrangements made with the repository(ies) where the described dataset will be deposited

The preparation of the current Data Management Plan was conducted in collaboration with the faculty member responsible for data management at Université Gustave Eiffel. In adherence to Horizon Europe project guidelines, arrangements have been established to ensure the proper deposition of the dataset in the Zenodo repository. If necessary, the university prepared to initiate contact with professionals experienced in utilizing Zenodo, facilitating ongoing communication and coordination to address any specific requirements or considerations for dataset deposition. This collaborative approach ensures that the repository arrangements align with best practices and meet the standards outlined by Horizon Europe for effective data management within the SHAREWIND project.

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

Yes

3.2.1.6 Does the repository(ies) resolve the identifiers to a digital object?

The project repository utilized in this project is equipped with the capability to assign Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs) to datasets and outputs. DOIs serve as persistent identifiers, ensuring the unique and enduring reference to digital objects, including research outputs and datasets. By adopting DOIs, the repository enhances the findability and accessibility of the SHAREWIND project's datasets, aligning with best practices in research data management and contributing to the broader scholarly ecosystem's interoperability.

3.2.1.7 Does the repository support versioning?

Yes

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

SHAREWIND - Shared anchors for floating wind turbines

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

Datasets and associated publications will be openly available on Zenodo. There are no intentional restrictions on sharing these datasets, and the default access mode is set to open. This approach aligns with the principles of openness and transparency in research data management. No legal or contractual reasons exist that would necessitate restricted access. In the event of any specific constraints related to the Grant Agreement, the project will adhere to the stipulated terms and conditions, ensuring compliance with legitimate interests and contractual obligations.

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

No

3.2.2.8 Is the described dataset / output supported by a data access committee?

No

3.2.2.9 Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends

To ensure accessibility during and after the SHAREWIND project, we have devised a comprehensive strategy for accessing the dataset/output. During the project, authorized project team members will have direct access to the dataset through secure, password-protected servers of the Université Gustave Eiffel. Regular backups will be implemented to prevent data loss, and access controls will be enforced to protect the confidentiality and integrity of the information.

After the project, the datasets are preserved in the project repository in Zenodo with their corresponding persistent identifiers to ensure long-term accessibility. This approach facilitates widespread access to the dataset by the research community, practitioners, and other stakeholders, contributing to the longevity and impact of the SHAREWIND project's outcomes.

3.2.2.10 Please specify how long after the project has ended the dataset / output will be made accessible for

By choosing Zenodo, data is stored in the CERN Data Center. Both data files and metadata are kept in multiple independent replicas. The data will be preserved for at least 20 years in the data repository. This preservation duration exceeds the standard practices and aligns with the long-term commitment to accessibility and openness, ensuring that the SHAREWIND project's datasets remain available for an extended period after the project's completion. Researchers, practitioners, and other stakeholders will have sustained access to the dataset, fostering ongoing utilization and potential contributions to future research and applications.

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

All metadata associated with the described dataset/output will be available as Public Domain under the Creative Commons Zero (CC0) license. Despite any potential restrictions on sharing the dataset itself, providing open access to metadata ensures transparency, discoverability, and potential collaboration opportunities within the research community. The use of the CC0 license indicates a commitment to making metadata freely available for public use, contributing to the overall accessibility and visibility of the project's information.

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

Yes

The metadata description will include details on how to access the described dataset. If necessary, hyperlinks will be incorporated into the metadata to facilitate easy navigation for users seeking access to the dataset. This approach ensures that users, researchers, and stakeholders can efficiently

locate the information needed to access and utilize the SHAREWIND project's dataset, enhancing the overall user experience and promoting seamless data discovery and retrieval.

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

Yes

Metadata will persist and remain available even if the dataset or output is no longer accessible. A strategic approach involves storing and managing metadata separately from dataset files and utilizing persistent identifiers for metadata records. This ensures that the valuable information encapsulated in the metadata, including details about the dataset, will endure independently of the dataset's availability. By employing this strategy, the SHAREWIND project safeguards the continuity of metadata accessibility, promoting ongoing transparency and documentation of the dataset's attributes, even in scenarios where the dataset itself may no longer be accessible.

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

No community agreed standards exist for the project discipline. To ensure interoperability, the data will be documented with README files and Data Reports. Metadata in Zenodo is compliant with the DataCite schema, which provides a standardized and structured framework for describing research outputs. While a controlled vocabulary may not be applicable in the project discipline, the use of README files and Data Reports, along with compliance with the DataCite schema, ensures clarity and consistency in documenting and describing the dataset, promoting effective data management practices within the given context.

3.3.2 If you created the vocabulary, where can it be found?

Not applicable.

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

No

3.3.4 Will you provide a mapping to more commonly used ontologies?

No

Not applicable.

3.3.5 What is the methodology followed?

Not applicable.

3.3.6 What community-endorsed interoperability best practices are followed?

Not applicable.

3.3.7 Does the described dataset / output provide qualified references with other outputs?

Yes

The described dataset/output in the SHAREWIND project has been designed to include qualified references with other outputs, creating meaningful links to enrich contextual knowledge about the data.

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

All data and accompanying documentation needed to validate the results of the research will be made available under a CC-BY license using Zenodo, in line with the Grant Agreement. This license choice aligns with internationally recognized standards and ensures that the research outputs are openly accessible, allowing for reuse, redistribution, and further contributions to the scientific community while adhering to the requirements outlined in the Grant Agreement and Horizon Europe guidelines.

3.4.2 What reusability and / or reproducibility methods are followed?

- Readme files
- Other

Readme files and detailed data reports will be included with the datasets to allow the reproducibility of the methods employed in the research project. These supplementary materials serve as essential documentation, providing comprehensive information on the methodologies, procedures, and analyses conducted during the research. By including detailed documentation, the SHAREWIND project enhances the reusability and reproducibility of its datasets, supporting transparency, and fostering trust within the research community.

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

Yes

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

The data will be kept and stored in the project repository in Zenodo during and after the project. This strategic choice of using Zenodo as the project repository ensures that the data will be securely preserved and openly accessible to third parties for reuse in the long run. By leveraging the features of Zenodo, including persistent identifiers and compliance with open access standards, the SHAREWIND project actively promotes the (re)use of its data by third parties, contributing to the sustainability and impact of the project's outcomes beyond its immediate duration.

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

A track of versions and modifications of the datasets is provided in Zenodo.

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

Other

In the SHAREWIND project, we have established comprehensive procedures for quality assurance to ensure the integrity and reliability of our research data. These documented procedures encompass a range of practices aimed at validating the cleanliness, consistency, and overall quality of the data. To achieve this, we employ tools and scripts tailored to the specific characteristics of our dataset, enabling automated checks for duplicates, inconsistencies, and proper data structuring. Our quality assurance framework is designed to address potential errors at various stages of the data lifecycle, from collection to analysis. These procedures are documented in detail, outlining the specific checks performed, the tools utilized, and the criteria for data validation. Regular audits and reviews will be conducted to maintain the effectiveness of our quality assurance measures, providing confidence in the accuracy and reliability of the research data throughout the project's duration. Any updates or modifications to these procedures will be duly documented and communicated, ensuring transparency and adherence to best practices in research data management.

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

1000

Euro

- Storage
- Archiving

Indirect cost

Regarding infrastructure costs: Digitization, Storage, Licensing, Sharing and Re-use and Archiving, it was estimated a cost of around 1000 Euros to acquire external hard drives to store backup data in addition to the local drives at the geotechnical centrifuge laboratory. Zenodo was selected as it has the advantage of being a free repository and offer a limit of 50GB per dataset.

Regarding skill costs that comprise data wrangling, description and documentation, metadata generation, formatting and cleaning it was estimated a cost in terms of time, leading to 2 days of work per month of the researcher Cristian Soriano.

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Other

Allowance of resources from the project grant using the research, training and networking contribution of the project which also will cover the fees to ensure Gold Access to the associated publications in peer reviewed journals to ensure its open access.

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

Cristian Yair Soriano Camelo (orcid:0000-0001-9530-0185)

Project Experienced Researcher in charge of the administration and generation of the Data Management Plan of the project.

5.1 Data Security

5.1.1 What security measures are followed?

- Passwords
- Physical access control

During the course of the research project, all data will be stored on local servers maintained and automatically backed up by the Université Gustave Eiffel. Every night, data will be automatically backed up, and recovery measures are in place through the Université Gustave Eiffel ICT services in the event of an accident. Access to the designated server is restricted to laboratory team members, including Cristian Soriano, Luc Thorel (project supervisor), and laboratory director Matthieu Blanc.

Additionally, datasets will be stored in the Université Gustave Eiffel cloud service, where access is granted using university identifiers and passwords. The cloud service serves as an additional backup and an alternative for online access to datasets.

After the project, the datasets will be published in Zenodo with an open access license CC-BY, ensuring continued security measures and accessibility for broader use and dissemination.

5.1.2 What conditions do the security measures meet?

- Data access
- Data storage
- Data recovery
- Data sharing

The security measures implemented in the SHAREWIND project adhere to conditions aimed at safeguarding the confidentiality, integrity, and availability of the research data. The data provisions include robust strategies for secure storage, archiving, and transfer of sensitive data. Here are the specific conditions met by our security measures:

Confidentiality: Security measures ensure that access to sensitive data is restricted to authorized personnel only. Access controls, including user authentication and authorization mechanisms, are in place to prevent unauthorized access.

Integrity: The integrity of the data is preserved through the implementation of data validation checks and checksums. These measures detect and alert to any unauthorized alterations to the data, ensuring its reliability and trustworthiness.

Availability: To ensure data availability, regular backups are conducted, and redundant storage systems are employed. These measures mitigate the risk of data loss due to hardware failures or unforeseen events, promoting continuous access to the research data.

Data Recovery: In the event of data loss or corruption, a comprehensive data recovery plan is in place. Regularly scheduled backups, stored in secure locations, facilitate the restoration of data to a known and reliable state.

Secure Storage/Archiving: Research data is stored and archived in secure environments with controlled access. These environments comply with industry standards for data security, and the storage infrastructure is designed to withstand potential risks, such as physical threats or cyberattacks.

Transfer of Sensitive Data: When transferring sensitive data, secure protocols, such as encryption, are employed to protect data during transit. These measures ensure the confidentiality of the information as it moves between different systems or collaborators.

5.1.3 How will you preserve the described dataset / output in the long term?

As previously mentioned, Zenodo guarantees storage for at least 20 years, ensuring a long-term preservation commitment. In addition to Zenodo, local copies of all datasets will be preserved on the Université Gustave Eiffel servers, providing an additional layer of security and redundancy. Furthermore, external hard drives will be kept in the laboratory facilities, serving as another measure to safeguard the datasets. These multi-tiered preservation policies and practices ensure the resilience and longevity of the described dataset/output, mitigating the risk of data loss and supporting sustained access for future research and use

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

no

Not applicable

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

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